

PCoA plot, link to Fig. 10B,
Appendix S2, plot S8

Fig. D4. Genetic Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) by population including all individuals of *C. quamash* ssp. *linearis* (tan to yellow circles), and *C. q.* ssp. *breviflora* in the California Floristic Province (CFP, n = 8) for broad-ranging western sites (n = 4). See Fig. 10B, Appendix S2 Plot S8. Site codes in Table 1 and Fig. 2 map.